

Original Research

Problems and Prospects of Handloom Industries: A Regional Study

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Abstract

The handloom textile industry, one of the significant labor-contributing industries in Bangladesh, provides income and employment opportunities for a sizable section of rural labor. However, in recent years, the handloom textile industry has been experiencing several problems in its production. The residents of three Upazilas in the Sirajganj district rely directly or indirectly on this sector. This study will examine the issues and opportunities of the handloom industry in three Upazilas of the Sirajganj district in Bangladesh. The district of Sirajganj was chosen as a purposive sample and used the multistage random sampling method of fifty handloom units from twenty villages in Ullapara, Shahajdpur, and Belkuchi Upazila. The Cobb-Douglas production function is used to identify in this case to assess the variables' impact on the Handloom sector's annual income. Labor, input, and education coefficient is significant at 1 percent of the level. On the other hand, capital has negatively impacted the handloom industries and is also not statistically significant. Despite experience positively impacting the handloom weaver's income, it does not influence statistically significant. The estimated capital coefficient of -0.208, and the approximate labor cost is 25.73. Major problems of the handloom industry in the high rate of fabrics and colors. These results suggest that labor is a vital part of the handloom industry and with the posting of workers, handloom output rises as well.

Keywords: Handloom Industry, Cobb-Douglas, Socio-Demographic, Bangladesh.

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Introduction

The handloom industry is one of Bangladesh's most potential and traditional weaving industries (M. Islam & Hossain, 2022). It is one of the most potential industries in Bangladesh, whose fragile present situation, had a remarkable past and may have a bright future (M. Islam & Hossain, 2012). It provides income and employment for a sizeable section of rural labor groups. Handloom was formerly the second largest employer and source of revenue in rural areas, behind agriculture. According to the Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics (Bangladesh Statistics, 2018) the result of the significant demand for its products in India and Europe, it has a long history of success. Well-known handloom items include renowned Muslins, Jamdanis, Benarashis, etc. Surprisingly, the industrial revolution and the development of contemporary technologies progressively altered the landscape. Bangladesh's highest possible indigenous sector is handloom (2020)

The term Handloom refers to any loom other than a power loom. A hand-operated machine for making clothing. In such cases, the regrowing process can be carried out entirely by foot (Kiron, 2014). An alternative method for weaving textiles is using a handloom, and its equipment, or a tool made of wood with just some iron components. The deceased handloom's body of the dead handloom is powered solely by a guy's hands and feet. The handicraft industry has the potential to have significant micro and macroeconomic effects on Bangladesh's economy (Liton et al., 2016a).

But compared to other countries, the overall development of *Small and Medium-sized Enterprises* (SMEs) in Bangladesh has not been much. According to the Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics (BBS, 2018), the SME sector contributes 20 to 25 percent to the GDP of Bangladesh. The SME sector contributes 55 percent to the GDP of The Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) member countries. Even in our neighboring country India, its contribution is about 45 percent. The SME sector contributes 60 to 70 percent to the GDP of China, Japan, and South Korea. Most of the employment is also in their SME sector. So the way it magnifies or relies on the contribution of big industry or big trade is wrong. And the general tendency toward the big industry is also one of the reasons for the neglect of the SME section. 40 to 45 percent of the workers are involved in the SME sector in Bangladesh. So the more significant the SME sector, the bigger the scope of employment (BBS, 2020). Fluctuations in volume and growth of small and cottage industries have been noticed in the past years. Its contribution to GDP in FY 2013-14 was 6.33 percent, which decreased to 4.60 percent in FY 2010-21, although the benefaction of the Small & Cottage Industry in FY 2016-17 was a maximum of 11.20 percent in GDP.

Table 1. The Volume and Growth Rate of Small & Cottage Industries in GDP

Type of Industry	2013-14	2014-15	2015-16	2016-17	2017-18	2018-19	2019-20	2020-21
Small and cottage	26113.1	28342.6	30909.4	33945.8	37086.4	41148	42778.1	43519.1
Percentage of GDP	6.33	8.54	9.06	11.20	9.25	10.95	3.96	1.73

Source: BBS, 2020

In Table 1, it is shown that the percentage of the Growth Rate of Small & Cottage Industries in GDP is declining over time. The handloom industry generates remarkable benefits for Bangladesh's economy regarding micro and macroeconomic impacts. It plays a vital role in reducing poverty, increasing employment, and enhancing household income and consumption in the country. Thus, in Bangladesh, The handloom sector has a positive contribution to employment generation and economic growth. But this sector faces various challenges which are the reasons for the non-operation of looms. Therefore, government and non-government agencies should come forward with financial, technical, and policy supports for developing the handloom industry in Bangladesh (Liton et al., 2016b).

In this context, the following questions will be addressed in this study. The research questions of the study are the following:

- What are the current problems of the handloom industries?
- What are the current prospects of this industry?
- Which kind of initiatives are needed to develop this sector?

In view of the above questions, the objective of this paper is to examine the problems and opportunities of the handloom industry in the study area.

The rest of the paper is organized into six parts. Following the introduction, the second section includes the literature reviews. The following order organizes the study's data, model and methodological framework, results and discussion, and finally discusses conclusions and recommendations.

Literature Review

An overview of the conclusions from the earlier literature is provided in this section. Also included here are some relevant findings from other nations. Some types of literature about the handloom industries will be discussed in detail in this section.

(Sangeetha & Charles, 2019) examined the Handloom wearers' problems and prospects in Thanjavur, Tamilnadu, India. This research is based on both primary and secondary data sources. Using the structured questionnaire and the personal interview method, they collected preliminary data from 120 respondents. This is a descriptive study, and the data have been gathered through in-depth interviews and semi-structured questions were asked. The secondary data was found in books, periodic journals, and articles relevant to this study. This study aims to understand issues confronting handloom weavers in Varanasi, Uttar Pradesh. The problems at stake are the invention of new technology (the power loom), capitalist domination, wage stagnation, and increased yarn price. (Das, 2016) carried out a survey of the present scenario and some problems of the Handloom industry in cooch behar district West Bengal, India. His study was derived from primary and secondary sources of data. He discovered that the climate was deteriorating due to illiteracy, financial limits, health issues, middle intermediaries, and government assistance. This study was done in coach Behar district India. In this study,

he did not find out the problems behind the handloom weaving industry. (Vimalkumar, 2018) discussed the handloom industry's future and challenges. This study focuses on selected handloom enterprises in Jaffna and their production and sales concerns. In Jaffna's rural districts, both men and women weave as a way of life. This study includes nine handloom industries. Northern handloom weavers have a rich history of culture and generational talents, a challenge for the handloom industry's survival. Sarongs, bed sheets, towels, curtains, table linen, kitchen linen, readymade clothing, soft toys, hand woven carpets, etc., are handloom textiles. In this research, the items are of high quality and texture and have a solid market and worldwide demand. They discovered that the current handloom industries confront several issues and obstacles. After the conflict, the Northern Sri Lankan handloom sector encounters various obstacles. The sector, which employs many families, must be revitalized. (Rohitha & Bharathi, 2017) identified the issues faced by the handloom industry. The study draws the attention of master weavers from the undivided state of Andhra Pradesh, especially four districts, namely, Nalgonda, Guntur, Krishna, and Prakasam districts. This study adopted the quantitative methodology, where 365 master weavers were selected through the purposive sampling technique. The study findings reveal that the handloom industry in this district is unorganized. This reflects that the weavers face some problems. This study has limitations as it was conducted in four sections of the undivided state of Andhra Pradesh only. There may be other issues related to weavers' supply chain management practices in other communities. Therefore, the study inference can't be counted as general. Thus, this study gives scope for conducting further research in the future. (Liton et al., 2016a) analyzed the present scenario and future challenges in the Handloom industry in Bangladesh. They discovered around 183512 handloom weaving units in Bangladesh, containing approximately 505556 looms. The overall number of functioning looms is 311851, or 61.7 percent of total looms, while the remaining 193705 looms are inoperable. Additionally, they identified other issues in Bangladesh's handloom sector that contributed to the closure of looms, including a lack of finance, a scarcity of materials, insufficient technology, a flawed marketing system, and insufficient government backing. This study is too old to make policy. (M. K. Islam & Hossain, 2015) examined the determinant of technological efficiency of handloom in the kushtia district of Bangladesh. They collected 257 handloom units were chosen at random for the study. Technical efficiency is obtained using the Cobb-Douglas production function model. They found in the study area average efficiency of the handloom industry is 0.245 by the Tobit model. They also found significant findings that influence the technical inefficiency of handlooms, such as the owner's expertise, education, and age, as well as the size of the unit. This study considered only the Kushtia district as the study area. (Rahman, 2013) identified the prospect of the handloom industry in Pabna district, Bangladesh. They considered five listed handloom industries in Pabna, Bangladesh. There are several factors that are negatively impacted the handloom industry in Patna. These include: a scarcity of lack of funding, higher material costs, lack of organizational capacity, inadequate technology and efficiency, a lack of government support, a huge knowledge gap, an inadequate power supply, and a scarcity of credit facilities, to name a few. Handloom industry issues are ignored in this study. (Narzary, 2013) concluded a survey of marketing problems and prospects of the handloom and handicraft industry which is based on 200 respondents who are the producer and retailers of the handloom and handicraft production. He found in his study that shows different market problems were faced by the producer and retailers in the study area. The study is based on the marketing

system of the handloom industry. (Akter & Ghosh, 2005) studied the handloom industry as it was on its way to extinction. In this industry, working capital, the high cost of raw material acquisition, a lack of organizational skills, insufficient technology, and a lack of legislative support are only a few of the significant variables contributing to the rapid pace of development. Their efforts to find out what was wrong and what was going to happen was futile at best.

Most of the studies have been completed on either problems or prospects of the handloom industry. Moreover, very few studies have been done on the hazards and opportunities of the handloom industry. But those studies are too old for policy making. There are very limited work has been done specially in sirajganj district. Although Sirajganj district is the most suitable area for handloom textile industries. For those causes, a field base study is necessary to find the problems and prospects of the handloom industry in Sirajganj.

Data, Model and Methodological Framework

Sampling and Data Collection

The study is based on field based data. Both qualitative and quantitative data have been utilized. The Sirajganj district was selected as a purposive sample. Because this district is nationally and internationally renowned for its handloom textile industries. In terms of district-based and family based handloom units, the position of the Sirajganj district is fifth highest, and this district has the second highest number of handloom factories in regarding the number of handloom in Bangladesh (BBS, 2018). After that, a multistage random sampling approach was used to select the relevant information from 50 handloom industries in the study area. The investigation involved twenty villages, five Unions, and three Upazilas of the Sirajganj district in Bangladesh. The data was collected via a standardized questionnaire administered to the handloom owner during the face to face interview. The timeframe of data collection was from June to September of 2021. There were both open ended and closed ended data collection questions.

Table 2. Sample Size and its Distribution (N=50)

Name of District	Name of Upazila	Name of Union	Number of Samples
Sirajganj	Ullapara	Durganagar	19
		Ullapara	1
	Belkuchi	Dhukariabera	12
		Bhangabari	4
	Shahjdpur	Shahjadpur	14
Total	3	5	50

Descriptive Analysis

Descriptive analysis is used to portray the information about age (Year), education (Year of Schooling), experience (year), number of handloom machines (Number), labor cost/day (BDT), input cost/day (BDT), capital, yearly income (BDT), production cost (BDT), and selling cost of the handloom product (BDT). In addition, the present problems

and prospects of the handloom have been illustrated. It is also acclimated to organizing, summarizing, and designating the relationship between two or more variables. It is also used for analyzing frequency, percentage and rank, etc.

Functional Analysis

The following equation illustrates how the Cobb Douglas production function was constructed and used to estimate the effects of variables on the owner's yearly income variation.

$$Y_i = \alpha + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 X_4 + \beta_5 X_5 + u_i \quad (1)$$

The Cobb-Douglas production function model is used to estimate the effects of variables on the annual income from the Handloom industry. For this reason, we consider the Cobb-Douglas type production function in this study.

The Cobb-Douglas production function model is used in this case to assess variables' impact on the handloom sector's annual income. As a result, this study takes into account the Cobb-Douglas type production function, i.e.,

$$\ln y = \ln \alpha + \beta_1 \ln X_1 + \beta_2 \ln X_2 + \beta_3 \ln X_3 + \beta_4 \ln X_4 + \beta_5 \ln X_5 + u_i \quad (2)$$

Where, Y_i = Income, α = Intercept, $B = \beta_1$ to β_5 Coefficients, X_1 = Capital, X_2 = Labor Cost, X_3 = Input Price, X_4 = Experience, X_5 = Education, u_i = Error terms.

Specifically, it is assumed in this case that there is no serial correlation and no covariance between the error term and the explanatory variable when the mean value of the error term is zero. Ordinary least squares (OLS) are used to find the most appropriate estimation approach, and they are utilized to estimate the empirical model (Husain, 2016).

Results and Discussion

Socio-Economic Status of the Respondents

A technique of defining people based on their age, education, job type, family size, and income, among other things. Low, medium, and high socioeconomic status are common classifications. Lower socioeconomic level people often have fewer access to financial, educational, social, and health resources than higher socioeconomic status people (Husain, 2016).

Age of Respondents

The handloom owner's age is an absolutely crucial component of any income generated by people in any workplace. The highest age group respondents in this study are 35-39 & 50-54. Both are 18 percent. The second highest age group of handloom owners is 45-49 and 55-59; both contain 16 ratios of the total number. The lowest age group of the handloom owners are 25-29 and 30-34 with 4 percent of respondents only. It indicates that that young people do not want to be professionals in this sector. Because of the fragile situation of the handloom textile industries.

Table 3. Age Distribution of Handloom Industry's Owner

Age of Group	Frequency	Percentage	Cumulative Frequency
25-29	2	4	4
30-34	2	4	8
35-39	9	18	26
40-44	6	12	38
45-49	8	16	54
50-54	9	18	72
55-59	8	16	88
60-64	6	12	100
Total	50	100	

Education Level of Handloom Firm Owner

To present the educational status of the handloom unit owner, years of schooling have been utilized, i.e., (i) 0 year, (ii) 1 to 5, (iii) 6 to 10, (iv) 11 and above. Table 4. exhibits the educational status of the handloom unit owner. The table shows that most of them had never gone to school, indicating illiterate. It can be seen from the table that the percentage of illiterate groups is 40 percent. Thirty-six percent of handloom farm holders were 1 to 5 years of schooling, and 16 and 42 percent had 6 to 10 years of schooling and 11 and above levels of education, respectively. It demonstrates that the majority of the handloom industry owner has no primary education.

Table 4. Years of Schooling Handloom Owner

Years of Schooling	Number	Percentage	Cumulative Frequency
0	20	40	40
1-5	18	36	76
6-10	8	16	92
11-Above	4	8	100
Total	50	100	

Occupations of the Handloom Owner

The significant parts of the handloom are occupied in their loom business. Eighteen percent of handloom farm owners are engaged in their own businesses. Only six percent of owners have been involved in agriculture besides their loom business. It can be seen that 12 percent of farm owners have been continuing loom business and others' work. Only 2 percent of handloom owners are doing services with their loom business. It implies that the majority of persons participating in the handloom industry rely only on this industry.

Figure 1. Occupation of Handloom Industry’s Owner

Family Size of Handloom Industry’s owner

This study categorizes family types based on the fact that all family members live together and eat in the same kitchen under the leadership of the family head. A family is classified into three categories small, medium, and large. Here, family members are those who take meals and live together. In a small family, the number of family members is not more than four. In medium and large families, the family numbers are equal to five and equal to or more than six, respectively. In this study, most respondents' families are medium with 48 percent. The small and large families are 26 percent with 13 frequency. So, the handloom owners basically own a medium size family.

Table 5. Family Size of Handloom Industry’s Owner

Particulars	Frequency	Percentage	Cumulative Frequency
Small ≤ 4	13	26	26
Medium=5	24	48	74
Large ≥ 6	13	26	100
Total	50	100	

Experience in Operating Handloom Industry

The total production of handloom products little bit depends on the experience of the handloom owner experience. Considering Table 5.5, among all those areas, 10 percent of respondents’ experience is 5-10 years, 12 percent of respondents experience 11-15 years, and 22 percent experience is 16-20 years. And 14, 14, 10, and 18 percent of respondents experience 21-25, 26-30, 31-35, 36-Above years respectively.

Table 6. Experience of Handloom Industry's Owner

Experience Range (Year)	Frequency	Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
5-10	5	10	10
11-15	6	12	22
16-20	11	22	44
21-25	7	14	58
26-30	7	14	72
31-35	5	10	82
36-Above	9	18	100
Total	50	100	

Monthly Income of the Respondents from Loom Business

Table 7. shows the monthly Income Distribution of the handloom industry's owners.

Table 7. Monthly Income Distribution of Handloom Owners from Handloom Business

Monthly Income	Frequency	Percentage	Cumulative Frequency
1001-3000	6	12	12
3001-5000	4	8	20
5001-7000	6	12	32
7001-9000	7	14	46
9001-1100	8	16	62
11001-13000	4	8	70
13001-15000	10	20	90
15001-17000	2	4	94
17001-19000	2	4	98
19001-Above	1	2	100
Total	50	100	

Table 7. shows that about 12 percent of respondents are included in the Income group 1001-3000, 8 percent in income group 3001-5000, 12 percent in income group 5001-7000, 14 percent of income group 7001-9000, 16 percent of income group 9001-11000, 8 percent of Income group 11001-13000, 20 percent of income group 13001-15000, 4 percent of income group 15001-17000, 4 percent of income group 17001-19000 and 2 percent of income group 19001-Above.

Handloom Farm's Owners loan Recipient and its Sources

Figure 2. shows that 58 percent of the handloom industry's owners have taken loans from formal or informal sectors, and the remaining 42 percent do not belong to the loan recipient. This shows that almost half of those who do handloom business will not get any loan assistance.

Figure 2. Percentage of Loan Recipients and Loan Non-Recipients

Handloom Farm's Owners' loan Sources and Interest Rate

Table 8. shows the sources of loans and Internet rates. Where most of the handloom owners borrowed from informal sources, i.e., loom Money lenders, 44.83 percent of respondents borrow from this source, and the rate of interest of loans taken from loom Money lenders can be seen in the informal sector as the lowest. Still, in reality, the interest rate is much higher than informal sector. In this case, a large part of the products has to be provided to the loom Money lender unconditionally, in a fixed amount and at a given price over some time. The second-largest source of loan for the handloom industry's owner is NGO, and 12 respondents received a loan from there, which is 41.38 percent of the total borrow. The interest rate of NGOs is 9 percent to 11 percent. The only institution source is Bank. Only 10.34 percent of respondents are taken loans from this sector. The lowest interest rate lender is the loom board. It gives loans in 2 percent. However, the number of their borrowers is also the quietest. Only one respondent was taken alone from there. It is shown that the rate of interest is too high to get a loan.

Table 8. Sources of Loan and Internet Rate

Sources	Frequency	Percentage	Interest rate
Loom money lender	13	44.83	0%
NGO'S	12	41.38	9-11%
Bank	3	10.34	11%
Loom Board	1	3.45	2%
Total	29	100	

Problems Existing in the Handloom Textile Industry

Handloom was one of the most promising small-scale industries in Bangladesh, but now it is full of problems. Sirajganj district, one of the weaving industries of Bangladesh, is not without these problems. The existing problems of the sample area weaving industry in this part are weavers have identified the biggest problem in the weaving industry as the price of dyes and yarns. The 100 percent handloom owner of this sample agrees. Since dyes and yarns are the primary raw materials of the handloom industry, the price of the

products depends on them. Due to the high cost of dyes and yarns, the production cost of the product is high, and the expected profit is not being achieved. Secondly, 96 percent of the weavers in this survey claim to get loans at an interest rate. As a result, they cannot go into production on a large scale. Capital problem and non-Cooperation of loom board, In both cases, there is a problem with the handloom industry, with 94 percent of handloom owners supporting it. 90 percent of handloom owners informed that the problem of handloom is preliminary research, old technology, and lack of incentives in the time of the downturn respectively. Along with these issues, bad weather problems, insufficient labor supply, and lack of industrial education hinder handloom production.

Figure 3. Problems that Existing in the Handloom Industry

Prospects that Enhance the Handloom Industry

Table 9. disclosed the critical factor that enhances the handloom industry boost in the production scale of the sample area. The total number of respondents is 50.

In the first phase, a favorable working environment gives total effort to all the firms. That study shows it is easy to get a fancy working environment to build the handloom industry. The second one is that living in the weaver community contributes 100 percent to handloom increase in handloom industries in this locality.

According to respondents, Positive things that enhance the handloom industry in this study are a third and fourth qualitative variable state that family business and easy market access can shock 90 percent. Almost 80 percent of the firm and the fifth and sixth available training and sufficient market selling push well enough in the handloom sector it's nearly 78 and 70 percent respectively. The crucial thing is that efficient transport

support has little opportunity for handloom owners, with only 52 percent adequate transport facility. And last one perfect weather, its make under the facility only 6 percent of the handloom industry got especial weather facility in this area.

Therefore above all, the positive affected is available, but the frequency percentage deviation varies spread.

Table 9. Positive Aspects of the Handloom Industry

No.	Main Opportunities	Frequency	Percent	Rank
i.	Favorable work environment	50	100	1
ii.	Living in the weaver community in this area	50	100	1
iii.	Family Business	45	90	3
iv.	Easy access to market	40	80	4
v.	Available training facilities	39	88	5
vi.	Sufficient market to sell	35	70	6
vii.	Efficient transport facilities	26	52	7
viii.	Perfect weather for making loom product	3	6	8

Result from Estimation of Cobb-Douglas Production Function

Using the Cobb-Douglas production function, the handloom firm's output and input are estimated here. The productivity of the handloom is examined using five explanatory variables. Table 10. provides an interpretation of the variables' effects on the handloom productions' yield.

Table 10. Estimation of Production Function

Explanatory Variables	Coefficients	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Pro.
Capital (X_1)	-0.21	0.112	-1.861	0.0694
Labor Cost (X_2)	25.74	8.848	2.909	0.006
Input Price (X_3)	11.51	3.588	3.207	0.003
Experience (X_4)	495.27	585.556	0.846	0.402
Education (X_5)	5943.91	1969.480	3.018	0.004
Constant	36956.80	181402.08	2.037	0.045
F-Value	17.50			
R-Squared	0.63			
<i>Dependent Variable: Yearly Income from Handloom, Number of Observations (N)=50</i>				

The estimated result shows that the constant is significant at 5 percent, and total labor, input cost, and education are necessary at 1 percent. The coefficient of multiple determinants of order square is 0.62. That means the explanatory variable is considered in the model that can explain the 62 percent of handloom weaver's yearly income variation. It implies that the interpretation of the handloom industry's owner income primarily depends on the explanatory variable considered in this model. Despite experience positively impacting the handloom weaver's income, its influence is not

statistically significant. On the other hand, capital has negatively impacted the handloom industries, and also its impact is not statistically significant. The explanation for capital's negative influence in the handloom sector is that the handloom weaving business continues to manage its production in the traditional manner. As a result, even if they have sufficient capital, the influence of capital has no effect on the handloom.

The estimated capital coefficient of -0.208 indicates that if the other factors remained constant, a 1 percent increase of capital would decrease the total revenue by 20.8 percent. The approximate labor cost is 25.73. That shows that the handloom weavers' income will increase by 25.73 percent change of labor cost change by 1 percent.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study sought to assess the problems and prospects of the handloom industry, the socio-economic status of handloom, and the current situation of the loom industry in the six unions of the three upozillas under the Sirajganj district in Bangladesh.

Preliminary data was collected from the owners of 50 handlooms from this region by using purposive and multi-stage sampling methods. Both tabular and econometrics techniques were used to analyze the collected data. The highest 18 percent response to this study was 35-39 and 50-54. Most of the handloom owners experience between 16 and 20. Which is 22 percent of the total respondents. 47 percent of handloom owners have a medium family, i.e., five family members who live and eat together. 1002-3000 BDT is the lowest income, and 19000 to above is the highest income level of this study. Ten people earn between 13001 and 15000, a maximum of 20 percent among the respondents. The co-efficient of total labor, input costs, and education is significant at 1 percent. Experience and capital are not statistically significant, but experience positively affects the handloom industry. In the handloom industry, the biggest problem is the high rate of input cost, which means the price of colors and fabrics is too high for production. All the respondents agreed with this point. Problems with getting the loan at low interest rate, capital problem/Insufficient capital, non-cooperation of loom board, inequalities in research and development, old technology, lack of Incentives in the time of downturn, lousy weather, the problem of transportations, insufficient labor supply, lack of industrial education these problems are significant obstacles to the development of the handloom industry in Bangladesh. Positive things which enhance the handloom industry are favorable locality/work environment, living of the weaver community in this area, family Business, easy access to market, available training, good call to sell, efficient transport facilities, and perfect weather for making loom products. Respondent thinks that favorable work environment, living of weaver community in this area these two reasons are the main ones.

In this situation, the following recommendations have been made to improve the weaving industry from this fragile condition.

Handloom industries need to be produced in conjunction with new information technology. The responsibility of maintaining the handloom industry locally rests with its board. Their role needs to be made more active. The quality of handloom products needs to be improved. So that, it can make competition internationally. This industry needs to

be expanded internationally without being confined to the country. The color and fabric market needs to be controlled; the government should subsidize this market. Loan arrangements need to modernize so that handloom units owner can take loans on easy terms and at low-interest rates. All the past famous handloom products have to be reproduced, so the industry regains its lost glory. Although the weaving industry is directly handicraft, weavers need training to maintain their design and quality. Since the problems of the handloom industry are particular, therefore, by solving these problems, the country's most potential small-scale sectors can play a determining role in the economy of Bangladesh.

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